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“Gymnasium Mostar” is gymnasium in Mostar, B&H; Formerly called Gimnazija “Aleksa Šantić” in honor of the eponymous poet, it is nowadays popularly referred to as Stara gimnazija (The Old Gymnasium). The school was ceremoniously opened on 26 October 1893.

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THE IMPACT OF ACUTE RADIODERMATITIS ON DEVELOPMENT OF THE ARM SYMPTOMS IN BREAST CANCER PATIENTS

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Background:

Radiation dermatitis (RD) usually occurs as an acute skin toxicity during breast cancer radiotherapy. Severity of RD depends on several factors, characteristics of patients, mode and duration of treatment. The incidence of severe RD can be significantly decreased by applying radiotherapy techniques and hypofractionated regimes. RD results from a high dosage of ionizing radiation of the skin during radiotherapy treatment which can limit patient's quality of life.

Aim:

The aim of the study was to determine the impact of RD, as an acute breast cancer radiotherapy complication, on the development of the arm symptoms.

Methods:

The study included 77 female patients treated at the Oncology Institute of Vojvodina who received radiotherapy after conserving breast cancer surgery. The EORTC-QLQ-BR23 questionnaire was used for the survey.

Results:

RD was registered in 31 patients (40.26%). The global assessment of the health status of the patients was evaluated with mean value 65.91. Patients rated the onset of arm mobility symptoms as 14.24. Patients with RD rated symptoms more intensively on the arm functioning scale (with RD 23.65 without RD 7.97). The observed difference in the assessment of functional arm symptoms was statistically significantly different in the case of functioning and mobility (r 0.17, p 0.000), indicating that the occurrence of RD correlated with more pronounced arm symptoms.

Conclusion:

Results demonstrated impact of RD during radiotherapy can influence the aggravation of the arm symptoms. Therefore, it is highly recommended to include physical therapy early in the treatment.

Key words: acute radiodermatitis, radiotherapy, arm symptoms, breast cancer

RARE CASE OF TRAUMATIC TRICEPS TENDON AVULSION RUPTURE

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Introduction:

Triceps tendon avulsion rupture is a very rare injury. Among all tendon injuries, triceps tendon rupture is the least common. In a large series of 1,014 muscle and tendon injury cases at Mayo Clinic, Annzel et al reported its incidence to be 0,78%. The usual mechanism of injury is a fall on an outstretched hand. Some cases have been reported as direct contact injuries. A 19-year old female patient was received in the emergency room after an injury of her right elbow sustained awkwardly by hitting the

edge of the dining table with her elbow while falling down on slippery floor.

Aim:

In this case report we are presenting a very rare case of triceps tendon avulsion injury caused by a direct hit, and open surgical repair of it as well as rehabilitation protocol

Methods:

patient was treated with open surgical repair with Krakow whipstitches pass-